

Assessment of Contact toxicity of Certain Pesticides to worker bees of *Apis Mellifera* L. under laboratory Conditions

Sushil Kumar

Department of Zoology, Government P.G. College Bisalpur, pilibhit-262201

Abstract

The present study was carried out to evaluate the contact toxicity of four organophosphate pesticides *i.e.* Dimetoate, Malathion, Quinalphos, Chlorpyrifos and one biopesticide, Neem oil to adult workers of *Apis mellifera* L (*A. Mellifera* L.). These organophosphate pesticides are among those of frequently being used to control different insect pests of major crops in North Indian states like Uttar Pradesh, Punjab, Haryana etc. The experimental setup was performed under laboratory conditions. Four different concentrations (*i.e.* 50 ppm, 100, 200 and 400 ppm) of each pesticide were taken against *A. mellifera* L. as per their recommended field doses. The data on mortality of *A. mellifera* L. was recorded at 1, 5, 10 and 24 hours after exposure to pesticides. To evaluate the toxic effect, median lethal concentration (LC₅₀) of each Pesticide was determined. The results so obtained, revealed that all pesticides were highly toxic after 24 hours of exposure at maximum concentration except Neem oil (Biopesticide). Dimetoate and Malathion showed the maximum toxicity with their LC₅₀ of 89.79 and 142.09 ppm, respectively while Quinalphos and Chlorpyrifos were moderate in toxicity with LC₅₀ values of 161.58 and 178.37 ppm, respectively. Neem oil, a biopesticide was found to be the least toxic with a LC₅₀ of 315.86 ppm after 24 hours of exposure to worker bees at the highest concentration of 400 ppm.

Key words: Contact toxicity, Biopesticide, *A.mellifera* L., Neem oil, Mortality.

Introduction

A large number of pesticides are being used in crop fields against the different types of pests all over the world. Unfortunately pesticides are not selective to pest species alone. Often non-target insects such as honeybees, which are economically important, are destroyed in the process of pest control (Atkins *et al.*, 1975).

Honeybees are regarded as one of the most important pollinators being involved in pollination of a number of crops and fruit plants of human importance, and in sustaining of wild flora diversity (Ollerton *et al.*, 2011). Honeybees play an important role by pollinating more than 75% of flowering plants across the world (Van Engelsdorp and Meixner., 2010).

According to Spivak *et al.*, 2010, about 35% of food supply is entirely dependent on pollinators all across the world among which honeybees are main contributors. Many nutritionally rich and economically valuable crops of food such as fruits, vegetables and fodders, entirely depend upon bees for their pollination. In many developed countries where agriculture is intense and mechanized, most of the agricultural crops totally rely on managed *A. mellifera* L. for pollination. From many years in the United States, 50 out of 250 crops are being pollinated from the colonies of managed honeybees (*i.e.* *A. Mellifera* L.) for the production of high quality commercial fruits and seeds (Kremen *et al.*, 2002).

The use of agrochemicals put a key pressure on insect pollinators (Belzunces *et al.*, 2012). Due to their indiscriminate use, colonies of honeybee are declining across the world. Agrochemicals can destabilize different types of pollinator communities before and after their application in the field crops (Potts *et al.*, 2010). If the production of fruits and seeds are pollen limited then there will be certain effects on pollination due to low and variable pollinators which ultimately decreases the crop yield (Garibaldi *et al.*, 2011). *A. mellifera* L. workers foraging in the field can be affected by getting in direct contact with crops treated with Pesticides (Koch and Weisser, 1997), or they get toxicants from fumes and dusts of Pesticides during their flight (Pierrick *et al.*, 2007). Pesticides also induce chronic toxicity in honeybees in terms of change in their foraging and learning behavior. Pesticides also affect their immune system (Kumar, 2017) and susceptibility to diseases (Desenex *et al.*, 2007; Pettis *et al.*, 2012). The decline of honeybee populations in the world is a serious problem. If this speed of their decline continues, the pollination of agricultural crops which depends upon bees will be badly affected (Fontaine *et al.*, 2006, Potts *et al.*, 2010). So it can cause the world food production at risk, because they are the main source of pollination for different crops, fruits and vegetables.

The present work has been designed to find out the contact toxicity of some commonly used organophosphate and one biopesticides (Neem oil) on worker bees of *A. Mellifera* L. being used on different fruits, vegetables and field crops to manage different types of insect pests in Indian crop field, so that awareness can be created among farmers and pesticide producing industries to use and develop only those Pesticides which have minimum effects to honeybees.

Materials and methods

1.1 Pesticides formulations

To conduct the present study, we used Commercial formulations of four organophosphate pesticides viz., Dimethoate 30 EC (Tata Tofcor), Malathion 50 EC (Aroxa), Quinalphos 25 EC (Kavach), Chlorpyrifos 20 EC (Ripsban) and one biopesticide Neem oil 25 EC (Surya) were purchased from their respective manufacturing companies to check their residual contact toxicity against *Apis mellifera* L. under laboratory conditions (Table I). We prepared four concentrations (50, 100, 200 and 400 ppm) of each formulated Pesticide as derived from their recommended field doses.

1.2 Collection of *A. Mellifera* L.

Newly emerged adult worker bees (*A. Mellifera* L.) approximately 3-8 days of age were used in this experiment during the month of June, 2018 and were identified from other bees on the basis of appearance of abundant light yellow setae on the dorsum of their thorax. During collection, these were kept in plastic cages to transport them in the laboratory. No hive treatments to control diseases were conducted prior to these studies. Hives were exposed to smoke twice for 30–60 sec prior to collection. These bees were fed upon 50% sucrose solution in the laboratory. The bees were immobilized by giving them cold treatment at -4°C for about 5-7 minutes. They were then allowed to recover from cold treatment and then kept under $30\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $62\pm 5\%$ R.H in darkness for 20 minutes prior to Pesticide exposure.

1.3 Preparation of Pesticide stock solutions

First of all, stock solutions of 400 ppm for all the Pesticides were prepared in solvents by adding calculated amount of each formulated Pesticide with the help of micropipette. Flasks were shaken thoroughly until Pesticides completely dissolved in solvents. The stock solution was then divided into two equal portions. One of them was reserved for treatment application and the volume of other portion was doubled by adding equal amount of solvent to make 200 ppm solution. In the same way, 200 ppm stock solution was divided into two equal portions. One of them was reserved for treatment application and the volume of other portion was doubled by adding equal amount of solvent to make 100 ppm solution. Above procedure was repeated with 100 ppm stock solution for making 50 ppm concentration of Pesticides.

1.4 Bioassay

Contact toxicity analysis of selected organophosphate pesticides to *A. mellifera* L. were conducted by Surface residual bioassay method as proposed by Radwan and Taha., 2012 using 2 liter plastic jars. These jars were washed out in potassium permanganate solution to remove all contaminations and then rinsed in distilled water four times. Finally, Jars were air dried before making Pesticide coating. 5 ml of each concentration (50, 100, 200 and 400 ppm) were taken in micropipettes and were applied into each jar, while in control treatment only 5 ml of acetone was applied. Then jars were shaken thoroughly so that concentration might reach every corner of the jars and were kept for drying for about 10 minutes. A group of 20 bees were released in each jar after it was completely air dried and were covered tightly with muslin cloths. These jars were placed on smooth and clean surface under $28\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65\pm 5\%$ R.H.

1.5 Data Collection

Data was recorded at 1, 5, 10, and 24 hours after treatment application. Mortality of bees was examined under stereoscope. All bees in a jar were put on the Petri dishes. Those which were moving actively returned into jars. A needle was inserted into immobile body of tested bees. Those which did not show any movement were considered as dead. Total number of dead bees were counted and mentioned in a data sheet.

Table I. List of Pesticides with common names, brand names, , chemical group and toxicity level.

Common name	Brand name	Chemical group of Pesticide	Toxicity level (as per Indian Standard)
Quinalphos	Kavach 25EC	Organophosphate	Yellow
Dimethoate	Tata Tafgor 30EC	Organophosphate	Yellow
Malathion	Aroxa 50EC	Organophosphate	Yellow
Chlorpyrifos	Ripsban 20EC	Organophosphate	Yellow
Neem Oil	Surya Neem 25EC	Biopesticide	Green

1.6 Data analysis

Statistical calculations were done according to Probit Method (Finny, 1971) to estimate LC₅₀, 95% Confidence interval for LC₅₀ and Chi- square test for each Pesticide used in this study. Each LC₅₀ determination was based on the different concentrations of Pesticides. Following formula was applied to correct bee mortality percentage (Abbott's, 1925) -

$$\text{Corrected Mortality\%} = \frac{\text{Observed Mortality} - \text{Control Mortality}}{100 - \text{Control Mortality}} \times 100$$

Result and Discussion

The results obtained for present study revealed that all the Pesticides were toxic for adult workers of *A. mellifera* L. at different exposure of time intervals and different concentrations (Table II and Fig.-1). The contact toxicity of Pesticides differed significantly at different concentrations and after different post-exposure intervals. The mortality of *A. mellifera* L. increased with the increase in concentrations of Pesticides and exposure periods. After 24 hours of exposure, the LC₅₀ value was 89.79 ppm for Dimethoate, 142.79 ppm for Malathion, 161.58 for Quinalphos, 178.37 ppm for Chlorpyrifos and 315.86 ppm for neem oil in case of with maximum concentration (400 ppm). However, there was a great variation in mortality and LC₅₀ of *A. mellifera* L. at 1, 5 and 10 hours after treatment. The current bioassays were performed as per criteria set by EPPO (1992), with the honeybees mortality rate less than 10% in control samples.

The order of toxicity observed for these Pesticides in this experiment on worker bees of *A. mellifera* L. was; Dimethoate >Malathion>Quinalphos>Chlorpyrifos>Neem oil. The results for comparison of % corrected mortality of *A. mellifera* L. at different concentrations of Pesticides and at different time intervals are presented in Table II.

It is well known that the negative impacts of pesticides have resulted decline in honeybee populations across the world (Neumann and Carrek, 2010; Henry *et al.*, 2012; Pettis *et al.*, 2012). According to Raghunandan and Basavarajappa (2013) the population of honeybees is decreasing drastically in different countries throughout the world due to use of Pesticides. The results relative toxicity of Thomas and Phadke, (1994) are in accordance to our current findings regarding Quinalphos and Chlorpyrifos . They reported that chlorpyrifos induced 100% mortality in three species of honeybees after 6 hours of its exposure at high concentration (0.06%) under laboratory conditions. Abrol and Rajinder (2003) also confirmed the toxic impact of chlorpyrifos to honeybees (*A. Mellifera* L.) by contact method of its exposure with a LC₅₀ of 0.0354 ug/bee however, they used topical application procedure with different concentrations.

The results of Sharma and Dharam (2005) and Letelier *et al.*,(2012) support this study as they reported highly contact toxicity of malathion and chlorpyrifos, the organophosphates, to *A. mellifera* L. at high cocentrations of active ingridients under laboratory conditions on the basis of their LD₅₀ value. The findings are in accordance with the current studies where they stated that most of organophosphates are highly toxic against *A. mellifera* L.under laboratory conditions by surface residual contact method after 24 hrs of their exposure.

The results of Bailey *et al.* , (2005) showed less toxicity of quinalphos, where it was considered moderate in toxicity; however, their method of its toxicity determination was different against *A. Mellifera* L. But, the findings of Akca *et al.* (2009) are in agreement to the results of this study, where they reported the acute contact residual toxicity of tested pesticides after 1, 8, 16 and 24 hrs after its exposure to *A. mellifera* L. where it proved to be highly toxic against bees under controlled conditions. According to Kumar and Gupta (2007), Dimethoate and Malathion showed the highly toxic effect against honey bees at its LD₅₀ and LC₅₀. Neem oil has been found

least toxic to honey bee *A. Mellifera* L. (Kumar and Gupta 2007 and Kumar 2017) so this biopesticide may be suggested to be used to manage pest attacks on crops but lots of experimental work is needed to find out the applicability of .

Table (II) Showing Contact toxicity of Four Organophosphate Pesticides and one biopesticide Neem oil on adult worker bees of *Apis mellifera* L. at different time intervals using surface residual method.

Pesticides	Exposure Time Interval (Hrs.)	LC ₅₀ (ppm)	Slope ±SE	X Value	Fiducial (C.I) 95%
Dimethoate	01	345.76	0.00286±0.00093	4.42442	311.17-894.6
	05	296.41	0.00281±0.00071	7.01623	195.67-455.2
	10	185.69	0.00432±0.00079	12.8965	101.88-161.3
	24	89.79	0.00606±0.00115	28.0013	39.07-121.6
Malathion	01	365.36	0.00272±0.00082	4.35452	289.4-995.6
	05	310.64	0.00300±0.00080	7.89654	276.8-596.71
	10	248.51	0.00326±0.00078	15.2314	180.64-359.2
	24	142.09	0.00462±0.00083	18.1935	119.3-221.33
Quinalphos	01	371.32	0.00277±0.00088	4.86562	293.87-766.7
	05	325.69	0.00268±0.00084	6.21457	264.7-695.34
	10	335.77	0.00297±0.00079	9.68220	242.87-596.8
	24	161.58	0.00430±0.00085	17.8256	98.20-205.9
Chlorpyriphos	01	367.21	0.00281±0.00082	4.22331	298.16-976.4
	05	341.96	0.00262±0.00081	8.54217	212.60-768.4
	10	349.00	0.00275±0.00076	12.2798	232.1-534.4
	24	178.37	0.00540±0.00094	15.1660	96.51-183.3
Neem Oil	01	397.89	0.00279±0.00089	4.72290	310.68-912.2
	05	372.36	0.00259±0.00086	7.30250	266.34-682.3
	10	362.11	0.00294±0.00077	9.21160	255.99-553.4
	24	315.86	0.00446±0.00081	14.9722	133.8-242.1

LC₅₀ of Pesticides used in parts per million(ppm) Confidence interval (C.I.) 95%; observations are showing different time periods and P<0.001 mean that results are highly significant.

Conclusion

The present findings on contact toxicity of Pesticides to honeybees (*A. Mellifera* L.) showed that all the organophosphate pesticides used in this study proved to be toxic when bees were exposed at different concentrations using surface residual method under laboratory conditions. This study revealed that there is an urgent need of limited use of these pesticides during blooming periods of flowers. So these findings suggest to conduct consistent reviews of different Pesticides and to discover alternates methods to protect not only our crops from pests but environment friendly organisms like honeybees also to ensure sustainable development and management of beekeeping for better pollination of valuable crops.

Acknowledgements

The author is grateful to Dr AK Gupta (Ex-Head, Deptt. of Zoology, SSV PG. College Hapur) who helped in creation of experimental Design of the problem. The author also pays his special thanks to Dr LS Gautam for guiding in statistical analysis. The author gives a special thank to Mr Rajesh Gangwar to provide apiry facility for the proposed study. A great thank is due to college administration whose cooperation and moral support made this work possible.

References

1. Abbott, W.S., (1925). A method of computing the effectiveness of an Pesticide. *J. econ. Ent.*, 18: 265-267.
2. Abrol, D.P. and Rajinder, S.A., (2003). Relative toxicity of some insecticides to *Apis mellifera* L. *J. Asia-Pacific Ent.*, 6: 235-237.
3. Akca, I., Tuncer, C., Güler, A. and Saruhan, I., (2009). Residual toxicity of 8 different insecticides on honey bee (*Apis mellifera* Hymenoptera: Apidae). *J. Anim. Vet. Advan.*, 8: 436-440.
4. Atkins E. L., MacDonald R. L., Greywood and Hale E. A., (1975). Repellent additives to reduce pesticide hazards to honeybees; Field tests. *J. Environ. Ent.* 4, 207-210.
5. Bailey, J., Scott-Dupree, C., Harris, R., Tolman, J. and Harris, B., (2005). Contact and oral toxicity to honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) of agents registered for use for sweet corn insect control in Ontario, Canada. *Apidologie*, 36: 623-633.
6. Belzunces L, Tchamitchian S and Brunet J. L., (2012). Neural effects of insecticides in the honey bee. *Apidologie* 43, 348–370
7. Desneux, N., Decourtye, A. and Delpuech, J.M., (2007). The sub-lethal effects of pesticides on beneficial arthropods. *Annu. Rev. Ent.*, 52: 81-106.
8. EPPO, (1992). Guideline on test methods for evaluating the side effects of plant protection products on honeybees. *OEPP/EPPO Bull*, 22: 203-215.
9. Finny, D.J., (1971). *Probit analysis*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
10. Fishel, F.M., (2010). *The EPA conventional reduced risk pesticide program*. UF/IFAS EDIS Document PI-224.
11. Fontaine, C., Dajoz, I., Meriguet, J. and Loreau, M., (2006). Functional diversity of plant–pollinator interaction webs enhances the persistence of plant communities. *PLoS. Biol.*, 4: e1.
12. Garibaldi, L.A., Aizen, M.A., Klein, A.M., Cunningham, S.A. and Harder, L.D., 2011. Global growth and stability in agricultural yield decrease with dependence on pollinator services. *Proc. natl. Acad. Sci. USA*, 108: 5909-5914.
13. Henry, M., Beguine, M. and Require, F., (2012). A common pesticide decreases foraging success and survival in honeybees. *Science Express*, March 29, 2012. 4 PP.
14. Koch, H. and Weisser, P., (1997). Exposure of honey bee during pesticide application under field conditions. *Apidologie*, 28: 439-447.
15. Kremen, C., Williams, N.M. and Thorp, R.W., (2002). Crop pollination from native bees at risk from agricultural intensification. *Proc. natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.*, 99: 16812-16816.
16. Kumar S., (2017). Effect of pesticides on glutathione s-ransferase activities in forager worker bees of *Apis mellifera* L. *Biochem. Cell. Arch.* Vol. 17, (1): 295-299.
17. Kumar, S., and Gupta, A. K., (2007). Age dependent Study of the impact of certain field pesticides on Acetylcholinesterase activity of *Apis mellifera* L. *J. Ento. Res.* 31(2), 115-119.
18. Letelier, L.C., Spina, Y.M. and Branchiccela, B.M., (2012). Acute contact toxicity test of insecticides (cipermethrin 25, lorsban 48E, thionex 35) on honeybees in the southwestern zone of Uruguay. *Chemosphere*, 88: 439-444.
19. Melisie, D., Damte, T. and Thakur, A.K., (2015). Effects of some insecticidal chemicals under laboratory conditions on honey bees (*Apis melifera* L. Hymenoptera: Apidae) that forage on onion flowers. *Afri. J. agri. Res.*, 10: 1295-1300.

20. Neumann, P. and Carreck, N.L., (2010). Honey bee colony losses. *J. Apic. Res.*, 49: 1-6.
21. Ollerton, J., Winfree, R. and Tarrant, S., 2011. How many flowering plants are pollinated by animals? *Oikos*, 120: 321-326.
22. Pettis, J.S., Van Engelsdorp, D., Johnson, J. and Dively, G., (2012). Pesticides exposure in honeybee results in increased levels of the gut pathogen *noseema*. *Naturwissenschaften*, 99: 153-158.
23. Potts, S.G., Biesmeijer, J.C., Kremen, C., Neumann, P., Schweiger, O. and Kunin, W.E., (2010). Global pollinator declines: trends, impacts and drivers. *Trends Ecol. Evol.*, 25: 345–353.
24. Pierrick A., Dominique F., Bruno M, Franck Marolleau, Jean-Noël Tasei, Jean-François Odoux (2007). Toxicity of dimethoate and fenoxycarb to honey bee brood (*Apis mellifera*), using a new in vitro standardized feeding method. *Pest Manag Sci.* 63(11) 1090-1094.
25. Prier, K.R.S., Lighthart, B. and Bromenshenk, J.J., (2001). Adsorption model of aerosolized bacterial spores (*Bacillus subtilis* variety *niger*) onto free-flying honey bees (Hymenoptera: Apidae) and its validation. *Environ. Ent.*, 30: 1188-1194.
26. Radwan, E.M.M. and Taha, H.S., (2012). Toxic and biochemical effects of different insecticides on the tomato leafminer, *Tuta absoluta* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Egypt. Acad. J. biol. Sci.*, 4 (1): 1- 10.
27. Raghunandan, K.S. and Basavarajappa, S., (2013). Analysis of multi-floral honey of the giant honeybee, *Apis Dorsata* F., for pesticide residues in Southern Karnataka, India. *Eur. J. zool. Res.*, 2:22-28.
28. Sharma, D. and Dharam, P.A., (2005). Contact toxicity of some insecticides to honeybee *Apis mellifera* (L.) and *Apis cerana* (F.) *J. Asia. Pacif. Ent.*, 8: 113-115.
29. Spivak, M., Mader, E., Vaughan, M. and Euliss, N.H., (2010). The plight of the bees. *Environ. Sci. Tec.*, 45: 34-38.
30. Thomas, J. and Phadke, K.G., (1994). Relative toxicity of oxydemeton-methyle, chloropyrifos and quinolphos to honey bees (*Apis cerana indica*). *Ind. J. agric. Sci.*, 64: 207-209.
31. Van Engelsdorp, D. and Meixner, M. D., (2010). A historical review of managed honey bee populations in Europe and the United States and the factors that may affect them. *J. Invertebr. Pathol.* 103, S80-S95.